

STAGES OF FORMATION OF VOLUNTARY QUALITIES IN FUTURE MILITARY SERVANTS

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Volitional qualities are formed in a person in real conditions, that is, they develop in the process of fulfilling requirements. D.A. Kasatkina said that moral qualities are formed from youth and are improved through the requirements of adults, as well as norms, laws and decisions existing in society.[1]

K. G. Dedyukhin pays particular attention to "Constructive activity", which is considered important for the professional activity of military personnel, and describes it as a mental activity aimed at identifying crimes, investigating, preventing risks, searching for hidden criminals, and planning quick actions. That is, in the process of cognitive activity, thinking mainly encourages finding answers to questions that are still unknown, or the power of thinking solves the situation.[2]

Analyzing this type of ability, V. M. Burkina calls it a type of ability, such as the ability to transfer and exchange information, to be able to follow the instructions of the organization, and to be able to organize work in difficult conditions. In addition, the type of communication skills required for a future military serviceman is also different, and in our opinion, no success can be achieved without mastering it well.[3]

According to A.A. Maksimov, the communicative activity of a military serviceman is the ability to receive the necessary information through communication, to solve practical and urgent tasks, to communicate directly with others, etc.[4] Therefore, in order to be able to influence others in the process of communication, every military serviceman should have high intelligence, knowledge, skills, and strong will.

In his research, researcher V.M. Smirnov focuses on some characteristics that are considered important in the military-professional training of military personnel, and distinguishes the following neuropsychic personal characteristics necessary for military personnel:[5]

- plasticity (flexibility) of mental processes;
- optimal level of reactivity and activity;
- hypersensitivity (increased neuropsychic sensitivity to external influences);

- the ability to resist (resistance to external and internal conditions that prevent the implementation of the started activity);[8]

- emotional stability;
- presence of high emotional intelligence;
- low level of anxiety;
- tolerance and nationality.

V. M. Statniy, while analyzing the activities of cadets of higher military educational institutions in his research, first of all distinguishes the following features of their voluntary actions leading to the achievement of the goal:[6]

1. Voluntary actions are conscious, purposeful actions performed by one's own decision;

2. In order to perform a voluntary action, there must always be acceptable grounds for performing the action, that is, objective and subjective conditions;

3. Voluntary actions - have a high motivational power manifested in the initial decision or its implementation;

4. Voluntary action is manifested due to the operation of certain mechanisms, which is additionally strengthened by goals, motivation, desire, need, decision, intellect, emotion, outlook and professional competence.

According to G.A. Nechiporenko, as a condition for the formation of important willpower in future military personnel, it is necessary to take into account psychological characteristics such as impulsivity and reasoning, prudence, memory and having a high level of general intelligence. is important.[7]

To sum up, volitional qualities are independent of given external circumstances, the mental dynamic formation process of a person is considered, and its main types are goal orientation, initiative, determination, endurance, self-control, independence, organization, courage, efficiency, etc. adjectives are included. Therefore, volitional qualities are considered the basis of mental actions, and it has a dynamic development stage.

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